

Oxidation of Phenylacetic Acids by Cerium(IV) Perchlorate

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The kinetics of oxidation of phenylacetic acids (H, *o*-Cl, *m*-Cl, *p*-F, *p*-NO₂ and α -C₆H₅) by cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid have been studied in aqueous acetonitrile medium. The reaction exhibits a first order dependence with respect to gross [Ce(IV)] and [phenylacetic acid]. A plot of k^{-1} versus [substrate]⁻¹ is linear with an intercept pointing to the formation of an equilibrium complex between the reactants prior to the main reaction. Effect of acetonitrile on the rate of reaction is quite interesting and has been investigated thoroughly. Effects of added H⁺ and salt have also been investigated. The stoichiometry is nearly four at constant [H⁺]. A suitable mechanism has been proposed to account for these observations.

THE oxidative decarboxylation of carboxylic acids have been carried out by metal oxidants¹ such as Ag(II), Co(III), Tl(III), Mn(III), Pb(IV), Ce(IV) and Cr(VI) species and non-metal oxidants such as *t*-butyl hypochlorite² and phenyliodoso acetate³. Cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid, ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) in nitric and perchloric acids and ceric ammonium sulphate (CAS) in sulphuric acid have been used as the cerium(IV) species. Cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid is the best oxidant among the various Ce(IV) species⁴ and its oxidation of acetic, chloroacetic, propionic, isobutyric and pivalic acids were reported in our previous paper⁵. The kinetics of oxidation of malonic acid^{6,7} and of several α -hydroxy acids^{8,9} have been investigated thoroughly. Oxidation of phenylacetic acid by CAN in nitric acid has also been investigated¹. In the present paper we report the kinetics of oxidation of phenylacetic acids (H, *o*-Cl, *m*-Cl, *p*-F, *p*-NO₂, *p*-OMe and α -C₆H₅) by cerium(IV) perchlorate in aqueous acetonitrile medium in the presence of perchloric acid.

Experimental

Cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid was prepared electrolytically from cerium(III) perchlorate as described earlier⁵. This was titrated with iron(II) solution and sodium hydroxide solution to determine the Ce(IV) and perchloric acid concentrations, respectively. Only monomeric Ce(IV) species was present in solution when prepared electrolytically⁶. Phenylacetic acids were crystallised from suitable solvents and their melting points were checked with literature values. Acetonitrile was purified by the standard procedure¹⁰ and perchloric acid (E. Merck) was used as such. All solutions for kinetic experiment were prepared with

conductivity water. Ionic strength was maintained by adding sodium perchlorate. The kinetic studies were conducted in aqueous acetonitrile medium at different temperatures, at constant ionic strength and pH. Kinetics were followed as reported in our earlier paper⁵. Since *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid reacted faster under these conditions, ceric ammonium sulphate in sulphuric acid was used. The volumes of CO₂ evolved from a known weight of phenylacetic acid in the presence of excess of Ce(IV) at different concentrations of perchloric acid were measured as suggested in decarboxylation kinetics¹¹ and are reported in Table 7.

Stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by estimating the Ce(IV) consumed and also by estimating the aldehyde as 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, after destroying the excess of cerium(IV) by Fe(II) sulphate. Spectral measurements were carried out by using PMQ II spectrophotometer. Potential measurements were made using OSAW slide wire potentiometer having a sensitivity upto a fourth decimal. The electrode was a 1 cm² platinum foil welded to a platinum wire and was treated as recommended by Sherrill *et al*¹² before its use. The Ce(III)/Ce(IV) half cell is coupled with a Pye saturated calomel electrode using a saturated ammonium perchlorate agar-agar salt bridge. The ϵ° values are presented in Table 5.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of substituted phenylacetic acids follows a first order dependence with respect to Ce(IV) species over a concentration range 2.47×10^{-3} M, as evidenced by the linearity of the plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time. At constant [HClO₄], ionic strength and temperature, $\log k_1$ vs \log [substrate] is also linear and the slope is almost unity for the acids (0.98). Hence the order with respect to substrate is also one (Table 1).

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TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF PHENYLACETIC ACIDS IN 30% CH₃CN (v/v)

[Ce(IV)] = 2 × 10⁻³ M

(a) [HClO₄] = 0.6 M; μ = 0.8 M; temp. 30°
 (b) [HClO₄] = 1.0 M; μ = 1.2 M; temp. 50°
 (c) [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 M; μ = 1.2 M; [CAS] = 2 × 10⁻³ M; temp. 20°
 (d) [HClO₄] = 0.6 M; μ = 0.8 M; temp. 35°

[PhAcOH] ^(a) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[<i>o</i> -ClPhAcOH] ^(a) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.245	0.59 ± 0.03	0.926	0.15 ± 0.02
1.625	0.77 ± 0.02	1.131	0.17 ± 0.01
1.990	0.96 ± 0.04	1.218	0.19 ± 0.01
2.500	1.30 ± 0.04	1.625	0.26 ± 0.03
2.882	1.40 ± 0.02	2.500	0.35 ± 0.01
4.000	1.85 ± 0.04		

[<i>m</i> -ClPhAcOH] ^(a) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[<i>p</i> -FPhAcOH] ^(a) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.926	0.15 ± 0.01	0.926	1.24 ± 0.15
1.135	0.18 ± 0.02	1.135	1.57 ± 0.08
1.222	0.19 ± 0.01	1.222	1.78 ± 0.06
1.626	0.25 ± 0.02	1.625	2.28 ± 0.04
2.500	0.38 ± 0.02	2.500	3.65 ± 0.11

[<i>p</i> -NO ₂ PhAcOH] ^(b) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[<i>p</i> -MeOPhAcOH] ^(c) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
2.005	0.51 ± 0.02	1.84	13.0 ± 0.5
3.015	0.86 ± 0.02	2.44	17.0 ± 0.5
3.500	1.11 ± 0.04	2.69	18.3 ± 0.4
4.017	1.58 ± 0.02	2.99	19.8 ± 0.4
		3.54	23.3 ± 1.3

[DiPhAcOH] ^(d) × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.414	1.41 ± 0.06
1.685	1.69 ± 0.04
1.912	1.86 ± 0.03
2.240	2.22 ± 0.11
2.500	2.99 ± 0.11

ammonium sulphate as the oxidant, the k₁⁻¹ vs [substrate]⁻¹ plot in the case of phenylacetic acid and *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid, there is no intercept in the k₁⁻¹ axis, indicating the absence of a complex or a complex whose formation constant is low enough to be kinetically determined. The reaction exhibited a positive salt effect. The reaction is considerably influenced by the variation in the acidity of the medium over a range of perchloric acid concentration (0.4-1.0 M) (Table 2). A plot of k₁⁻¹ vs [H⁺]⁻¹ is also linear. This is in agreement with the general observation that increasing the [H⁺] increases the concentration of the effective oxidant, namely the unhydrolysed Ce(IV) aq^{14,15}. The redox potential of the Ce(III)/Ce(IV) system also increases¹² with the increase in [H⁺]. Predominant cerium(IV) species is reported^{6,16} to be monomeric in electrolytically prepared Ce(IV) solution in the perchloric acid concentration range, 0.2-2.0 M.

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS IN 30% CH₃CN (v/v) AT 30°, AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Substrate acid	μ = 0.8 M [HClO ₄] = 0.6 M		
	k ₂ × 10 ⁸ dm ³ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹
Phenylacetic	4.80	101.4	87.6
<i>p</i> -Fluoro phenylacetic	15.10	79.4	84.7
<i>m</i> -Chloro phenylacetic	1.62	83.2	90.4
<i>o</i> -Chloro phenylacetic	1.63	74.0	90.3
<i>p</i> -Nitro phenylacetic*	0.41	75.2	94.0
Diphenylacetic	6.02	74.0	87.1
Phenylacetic**	0.10	—	97.3
<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenylacetic**	189.4	77.3	78.3

* [HClO₄] = 1.0 M; μ = 1.2 M.

** [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 M; μ = 1.2 M, CAS as oxidant.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [HClO₄] ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION

[PhAcOH]	Solvent, CH ₃ CN-H ₂ O 30% (v/v)	[DiPhAcOH]	[Ce(IV)]
1.625 × 10 ⁻³ M		1.685 × 10 ⁻³ M	1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M
[Ce(IV)]	2.0 × 10 ⁻³ M	[Ce(IV)]	0.8 M
μ	1.2 M	μ	35°
temp.	30°	temp.	35°
[HClO ₄] M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	[HClO ₄] M	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.40	0.66	0.60	1.69
0.60	0.79	0.80	2.24
0.80	0.87	1.00	2.61
1.00	0.96		

At constant ionic strength and [HClO₄], the plot of k₁⁻¹ vs [substrate]⁻¹ is linear, making an intercept on the rate axis pointing to the formation of an equilibrium complex between Ce(IV) species and the substrate prior to the main reaction¹³. The intercepts × 10⁻⁴s⁻¹ obtained for various phenylacetic acids are as follows: 0.11 = H, 0.54 = *o*-Cl, 0.13 = *p*-F and 0.07 = *α*-C₆H₅ at 35.0°. A deepening of the yellow colour of Ce(IV) perchlorate on mixing with the substrate, also substantiates the complex formation. However, spectral measurements are too elusive to give accurate values for the determination of the stability constants. But with ceric

The second order rate constants obtained from the pseudo first order constants are used for comparison, since the order with respect to the substrate is very nearly one (Table 3). The groups which increase the electron density at the reaction centre should facilitate the electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant and accordingly *p*-methoxy, *α*-phenyl and surprisingly *p*-fluoro compounds react faster than phenylacetic acid whereas *o*-chloro, *m*-chloro and *p*-nitrophenylacetic acids react slower as the attached groups decrease the electron density at the reaction site. A plot of log k₂ vs σ⁺ gives a ρ value of -1.9 ± 0.2. The correlation with σ⁺ and the negative ρ value suggest the development of a partial positive charge on the benzylic carbon atom during the cleavage step. For reactions leading to benzyl radical, ρ values are in the range -0.3 to 1.5¹⁷, while that involving cationic character at benzylic or benzydrylic centre ρ value is nearly -5.1¹⁸. *p*-Methoxy, *α*-phenyl and *p*-fluoro groups by releasing electrons, stabilize the partial positive charge formed at the benzylic carbon and hence increase the rate. The other three groups destabilize the positive charge and hence retard the rate.

The oxidation of *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid by cerium perchlorate in perchloric acid is exceedingly fast even at low temperatures. The +M effect of the *p*-methoxy group alone cannot explain this. In acid media the methoxy group may get protonated and if the protonated form is reacting, the reaction has to be slower than with phenylacetic acid, since it is an electron withdrawing group. The coordination of Ce⁴⁺ with the methoxy group of the acid is another possibility. For instance, the orange yellow colour of Ce(IV) solution changes to reddish orange by the addition of anisole. The absorption at 620 nm of a 0.005 M cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid in a 30% CH₃CN (v/v) solvent is decreased considerably on the addition of a 5% solution of anisole in the same solvent. The deepening of the yellow colour of Ce⁴⁺ solution on the addition of *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid indicates complex formation. But coordination of Ce(IV) with methoxy group of the substrate, like the protonation of the same group, should decrease the rate. Therefore, the oxidation of *p*-methoxyphenylacetic acid by this oxidant could be explained by a different mechanism probably involving a radical cation. Such a species was postulated in the oxidation of diphenylmethanes¹⁹ and fluorenes²⁰ by Cr(VI) and of toluenes²¹ by Mn(III) where *p*-methoxy group exerts a considerable influence on the rate

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT ON THE REACTION RATE

Solvent % CH ₃ CN	Second order rate constants × 10 ⁴ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹			
	Phenylacetic acid (a)	<i>p</i> -Nitro- (b)	<i>p</i> -Methoxy- (c)	<i>o</i> -Phenyl- (d)
30	4.80	2.72	7.06	9.87
40	3.81	—	2.88	6.98
50	3.38	2.26	1.36	6.62
60	5.05	2.40	0.88	6.98
70	5.72	—	—	8.22
80	21.42	—	—	—

 (a) [HClO₄] = 0.6 M; μ = 0.8 M; temp. 30°.

 (b) [HClO₄] = 1.0 M; μ = 1.2 M; temp. 50°.

 (c) [H₂SO₄] = 1.0 M; μ = 1.2 M; temp. 20°; CAS as oxidant.

 (d) [HClO₄] = 0.6 M; μ = 0.8 M; temp. 35°.

TABLE 6—DETERMINATION OF THE STOICHIOMETRY

[PAA] × 10 ³ M	[Ce(IV)] × 10 ³ M	[Ce(IV)] = 0.20 M; [Ce(IV)] [PAA]	[HClO ₄] = 0.6 M; Temp. 30°. Weight of 2,4-dinitro- phenyl hydrazone(g)	[C ₆ H ₅ CHO]* × 10 ³ M	[C ₆ H ₅ CHO] [PAA]
3.23	12.88	3.99	0.8610	3.01	0.93
3.83	16.13	4.11	1.035	3.62	0.95
4.34	16.87	3.85	1.179	4.12	0.95
4.40	17.99	4.08	1.150	4.02	0.91
4.96	19.26	3.88	1.299	4.54	0.93
3.83	19.95	5.21 ^a	—	—	—
4.13	18.31	4.43 ^b	—	—	—
2.34 ^a	9.29 ^o	3.97 ^o	—	—	—
2.51	10.10	4.02	—	—	—

* Calculated from the weight of 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone.

 a [HClO₄] = 3.0 M; temp. 35°.

 b [HClO₄] = 2.0 M; temp. 55°.

 c For diphenylacetic acid, [HClO₄] = 2.0 M; temp. 40°.

CH ₃ CN %	Mole fraction	Mole ratio CH ₃ CN:H ₂ O	ε° at 30°; μ = 1.2 M [HClO ₄] = 0.6 M Ce(IV) = Ce(III) = 2 × 10 ⁻³ M volts	Dielectric constant* (25°)
30	0.1225	1 : 6.84	1.637	65.6
40	0.1850	1 : 4.40	1.636	61.3
50	0.2542	1 : 2.93	1.635	57.0
60	0.3382	1 : 1.95	1.645	52.8
70	0.4331	1 : 1.31	1.681	48.6
80	0.5768	1 : 0.73	1.695	44.5

* Estimated graphically from percentage composition vs dielectric constants of water and acetonitrile.

The effect of varying the solvent composition is seen from Table 4. The rate of the reaction decreases with the increase in acetonitrile content of the medium and reaches a minimum at 60% CH₃CN (v/v). This is attributed only to the decrease in polarity of the medium which destabilises the partial positive charge on the benzylic carbon, in the transition state. No change in the redox potential of the system Ce(III)/Ce(IV) occurs in this range (Table 5). However, beyond 60% CH₃CN (v/v) it increases. This increase is reflected in the enhancement of rate in the solvent range 60-80% CH₃CN (v/v). The Ce(IV)-HClO₄-CH₃CN system shows additional absorption maxima at 265 and 293 nm, when the percentage of CH₃CN is 80%, compared to the system containing only 30% CH₃CN which shows absorption only at 252 nm. This may be due to CH₃CN molecules substituting some H₂O molecules in the inner coordination sphere of the Ce(IV) species, which would increase the oxidising power of the oxidant. But in the case of oxidation by ceric ammonium sulphate, which proceeds by an outer sphere mechanism, the rate decreases with the increase in acetonitrile content of the medium.

Further insight into the nature of the reaction is obtained from a study of the products and stoichiometry. The stoichiometry in the case of aliphatic acids is dependent on the structure of the acids²², but in the case of phenylacetic acids it is nearly four at constant [H⁺]. The product analysis yielded 93% of the aldehyde (Table 6). But the

stoichiometry of the oxidation of phenylacetic acid is dependent on $[H^+]$ and temperature, since benzaldehyde produced initially gets further oxidised to benzoic acid which in turn is oxidised. This is supported by the volume of CO_2 evolved in the reaction (Table 7). For the determination of stoichiometry the substrate was allowed to react with a known excess of the oxidant whereas the kinetics were carried out under pseudo first order conditions with the excess of the substrate, so that the rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol, the likely product formed initially from phenylacetic acid, may be neglected in comparison with that of the acid.

TABLE 8—OXIDATION OF PHENYLACETIC ACID BY DIFFERENT Ce(IV) SPECIES

Oxidant $\times 10^3 M$	$\mu = 0.8 M; [HClO_4] = 0.6 M$		k_2 $\times 10^4$ $dm^3 mol^{-1}s^{-1}$
	[PAA] $\times 10^3 M$	k_1 $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$	
Cerium(IV) perchlorate 1.85 M, temp. 30°	1.46	1.22	8.42 ± 0.53
	1.63	1.44	
	1.79	1.41	
	1.92	1.56	
	2.28	1.97	
Ceric ammonium nitrate 2.00 M, temp. 30°	1.63	1.53	9.42 ± 0.15
	1.99	1.83	
	2.50	2.33	
	2.88	2.81	
Ceric ammonium sulphate 2.00 M [H ₂ SO ₄] = 1.0 M; $\mu = 1.2 M$, temp. 65°	8.20	0.81	9.30 ± 0.40
	10.07	0.91	
	10.98	0.98	
	11.80	1.22	

The following scheme has been suggested for the reaction.

Since the step (4) can be neglected under kinetic condition the rate of the reaction is given by the following expression :

$$\frac{1}{k_1} = \frac{1}{k_t} + \frac{1}{k_t K [R\text{COOH}]} + \frac{k_h}{k_t K [R\text{COOH}][H^+]}$$

At 30°, μ , 0.8M and $HClO_4$, 0.6M; $k_t \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ for the phenylacetic acids are 2.29=(H), 0.47=(*o*-Cl) and 19.2=(*p*-F); the formation constant for phenylacetic acid is 0.15 $dm^3 mol^{-1}$.

In Ce(IV) oxidations, the activation parameters (Table 3) calculated from rate constants are due to the overall effect of the first three steps as suggested in the above scheme. k_h , K and k_1 may have different H^+ , μ and temperature dependences. Since

pK_a values of phenylacetic acids vary only slightly, the formation constant K cannot possibly differ much. ΔG^\ddagger values can be correlated with the substituent effects. An electron withdrawing group attached to the ring makes the substrate a poor reductant and thereby increases ΔG^\ddagger value, on the other hand an electron releasing group by stabilising the partial positive charge formed in the transition state decreases the ΔG^\ddagger value.

TABLE 7—VOLUMES OF CARBON DIOXIDE EVOLVED AT 757 mm PRESSURE

[PAA] $10^3 M$	[HClO ₄] M	Temp. °C	Expected ml	Experimental ± 0.4 ml
10.88	1.0	30	18.70	20.00
11.45	1.0	40	20.40	19.80
10.00	2.0	55	18.20	24.00
8.73	3.0	30	16.00	23.00

The rates of oxidation of phenylacetic acid with different Ce(IV) species, viz. cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid, ceric ammonium nitrate in perchloric acid and ceric ammonium sulphate in sulphuric acid are presented in Table 8. The order with respect to Ce(IV) is unity; but with respect to substrate it is very nearly one in the cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid and is one in the other two cases. Plots of k_1^{-1} vs $[substrate]^{-1}$ are linear in all cases; only in the case of cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid there is an intercept on the k_1^{-1} axis, whereas the lines pass through the origin in the other two cases. The rate of oxidation increases with $[H^+]$ in all the cases. Relative rates, $k_2 (\times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1}s^{-1})$ for cerium(IV) perchlorate in perchloric acid and ceric ammonium nitrate in perchloric acid are 8.42 ± 0.53 and 9.42 ± 0.15 at 30°, and at 0.6M perchloric acid and for ceric ammonium sulphate at 65° the rate is 9.3 ± 0.4 $\times 10^{-4} dm^3 mol^{-1}s^{-1}$.

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